

Introduction to containers kubernetes and openshift

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Containers:

- Containers are units of software that encapsulate all the software necessary to run.
- Containers are pretty much the same as VMs but, all containers will run on one operating system. And all containers are accessed by a “container engine” or “container runtime” instead of the hypervisor.

Most common dockerCLI commands:

- build: creates docker images on “ dockerfile”
- tag: to give a name to an image. Does not overwrites.
- images: lists all the images on the machine.
- run: runs an image that’s been built
- push, pull: stores and retrieves images from a remote source.
- PS: command to list the containers.
- container rm <container ID>: to delete a container.
- stop: to stop a running container.

Developing a container:

- Using a “dockerfile” which outlines steps to build an image using “build” command. Where the image is an immutable file means “ Read-only”
- When the “image” is run by a “run” command it will generate a “container”, for clarification: in OOP an image could be considered as a class and the container is an instantiated object of that class.
- In the building process the container is built according to the dockerfile where each instruction creates a layer of the image, and after running the image another layer is added which is the container but its Read-write.
- Each “dockerfile” consists of the following commands:
 - o FROM: which indicates the base image to be built on such as an operating system, or a specific language.
 - o RUN: which executes commands, so you can put a Bash command and execute a script.
 - o ENV: to set environment variables.
 - o ADD and COPY: as the name indicated it’s to add from remote URLs and copy files or directories to the image.
 - o CMD: only one per file to start running the file.

Container registries:

- Used to store and retrieve an image, used in open source or private registries
- To store an image use “push” and to retrieve an image use “pull”.
- The name of an image consists of: “hostname/repository: tag” ex: “docker.io/ubuntu:18.04”

Running an image:

- In a build command the “-t” (which is short for Tag) option specifies the name we want to give to the image.
- In the end of the command a period is a shorthand for the current directory.
- First thing happens when running a build command, the docker daemon gets called and each instruction in the “Dockerfile” gets executed.

Kubernetes:

- Container orchestration is for deployment, availability, scaling, scheduling, updates and health checks.
- Declarative management: which means a desired state can be expressed. For example, if there is an application desired state to be reached then Kubernetes will work to ensure that the current state matches the desired state.

Kubernetes architecture:

- API Server: all communications in the cluster utilizes this API.
- etcd: store all the data.
- Scheduler: assigns newly created pods to nodes, determine where the loads should run.

- controller manager: run all the processes that monitors the clusters state. And make sure that the current state matches the desired.
- sometimes there is a cloud manager and that would work to connect the cluster to a cloud.
 - Nodes: could be virtual or physical, and it's controlled by the controller manager, and the components on that node can then enable it to run pods.
 - Kubelet: communicates with the API, connects between the container runtime and the controller manager.
 - Kube-proxy: a network proxy, maintain network rules.
 - Controllers in Kubernetes works in a similar way to a room temperature thermostat, to keep the cluster at the desired state. Where it will contact API server to take action in case the current state does not match the desired state.

Kubernetes objects:

- objects: are simply the desired state that the workload needed to reach.
- the object consists of two parts the (spec and state), where the spec is the desired state while the state is the current state of the object.

Objects characteristics:

- Namespaces: used to virtualize a cluster, segregate a cluster by project, team, useful with large number of cluster users. Provides a scope for object names. A cluster has many namespaces.
- Labels: key/value pair attached to objects, to identify them and they are not unique. And used by selectors.
- Selectors: identify a group of objects.

Basic Kubernetes objects:

- Pod: the simplest object running in the cluster it could be a process or a single container or multiple containers sharing the same resources. And the objects get described in a YAML file.
- ReplicaSet: is a group of identical Pods connected together by horizontal scaling, a pod template is also defined in a ReplicaSet spec. And a selector to identify which pods the ReplicaSet can acquire.
- Deployment: provides updates for both pods and ReplicaSets, otherwise it has the same definition as a ReplicaSet.

Kubectl CLI: there is two types of commands in the "cube control" which is:

- imperative: which is the easiest such as create, update, delete. And to make replicating changes easier, and that is done by creating a template.

- declarative: most advanced and powerful form of commands in kubectl, which work on several changes and files when executed to get it into the desired state, can be said as imperatives are for files while declaratives are for directories. But both with the same command "apply"

Commands:

- Apply: used to apply a file to a pod or a cluster of pods.
- Get: list a number of resources. In the namespace.
- Describe: shows details about a resource or a number of resources. In the namespace. “Describe pod (pod name)” to show IP address and much more.
- Config get-clusters: to show the clusters there is.
- config get-contexts: to show the context in the namespace.
- get pods: to show all the pods in the namespace.
 - In the lab and before building and pushing the pod (container image) ran “export” command to set the namespace as an environment variable.

-run: to run an image as a container in Kubernetes, which is an imperative command

-delete: to delete a pod.

-create: to run a YAML file to create a pod

Now turn to declarative commands which more suitable for production environment:

- after running apply command to a deployment file, replicas will be created and now even if I delete a pod kubectl will create one to maintain the desired state specified by the apply command

-expose: to expose the pods to the internet, and creates a clusterIP service.

-proxy: create a proxy so the clusterIP become externally accessible.

Managing applications with Kubernetes:

Scaling:

- ReplicaSets: it manages pods by creating or deleting or ... to ensure maintaining the desired state.
- It is recommended to create a deployment instead of a replicaset since it has more features
- To scale a cluster’s replicas number you can use the command “Scale”.

Autoscaling:

- Horizontal pods autoscaler: will change the number of pods based on traffic
- May use “autoscale” command to set an autoscaling range for the cluster.
- Vertical scaling means increasing the computing resources dedicated to the deployment.

Rolling updates:

- To get updates add liveness and readiness probs to the deployment file.
- Add rolling updates strategy to the YAML file.
- May use the “set image” command to set the image to update the pods to.
- May use “rollout status” command to check the deployment update status.

- Rollbacks to the rescue: are possible in Kubernetes, and that is by using “Rollback undo” command.

ConfigMaps and secrets (storing configuration): ****a bit complex****

- Configmaps is a way to store configuration for deployments separately from the code, and make it accessible for other deployments too.
- It can be created in multiple ways: such as string literals or by stating a key=value pair in the “create configmap” command, creating a file that contain all the key=value pairs and in both cases the variables have to be added to the YAML file.
- And also, there is multiple ways to reference from a pod or deployment such as referencing as an environment variable or mount as a volume
- You can directly add the environment variable to the YAML file in “env:” section.
- Creating secrets is similar to creating config maps.

Service binding:

- It means binding a service to a Kubernetes cluster that we have created.
- In IBM cloud services we can use a service by binding it to a deployment we create, and that is by using a .Json file.
- Binding the service will provide us with credentials as a secret we can use when writing code which is JavaScript as the example shown.

Kubernetes ecosystem:

- Kubernetes is not an all-inclusive platform as a service, it’s more flexible than opinionated.
- The ecosystem provides many services that Kubernetes does not. Such as docker to build images and container registries to push the images to them, and even more such as logging, monitoring, CI/CD.
- Cloud native computing foundation which hosts Kubernetes provides a couple of resources to better understand the Kubernetes ecosystem.
- Cncf landscape shows all the open-source services available on cloud native development.

Red Hat OpenShift:

- It's a hybrid cloud, enterprise Kubernetes application platform.
- Hybrid cloud is an IT architecture that incorporates workload portability, orchestration, and management across on-premises and cloud environments. OpenShift can be run on-prem and in cloud environments.
- As an application platform, OpenShift does more than orchestrate containers—it also provides additional tooling around the complete lifecycle of applications, from build and CI/CD to monitoring and logging.
- OpenShift provides many services:
 - Platform services.
 - Application services.
 - Developer services.

- OKD (Origin Kubernetes Distribution): upstream Kubernetes distribution embedded in OpenShift, it adds developer- and operations-centric tooling on top of Kubernetes.
- We can make an analogy to the Linux kernel, Kubernetes is the kernel, OpenShift is the distribution.
- Now after knowing that, what is OKD? Well, Red Hat packages OKD with other software, resources, and official support to create a product, Red Hat OpenShift Container Platform, that it then sells.
- Similarities between OpenShift and Kubernetes: has Kubernetes capabilities, container orchestration, opensource software.
- Differences between them: Kubernetes is a project while OpenShift is a product. Kubectl vs oc where oc is a CLI contains Kubectl functionality, OpenShift has a web UI
- While Kubernetes Deployment objects are still present in OpenShift, DeploymentConfig objects are OpenShift specific.
- Deployment in Kubernetes is time consuming, managing deployments is easier in oc but Kubernetes is more flexible.
- Build: which is an automation tool available in Red Hat OpenShift , and CI/CD is an example.
- In OpenShift, a build is simply the process of transforming inputs into a resultant object. For example, the input could be source code in a git repository, while the result would be a container image.
- "Source-to-image" (S2i) is another build strategy offered by OpenShift. is a tool for building reproducible container images. S2i injects application source code into a container image to produce a ready-to-run Image. The new image is built by incorporating a builder image and the source. This eliminates the need to write a Dockerfile and lets you go from source to image in a single step
- Custom build: a custom build represents a more advanced strategy. Here, you must define a builder image that will be used for the build process, rather than relying on a builder image provided by OpenShift.
- Both the Docker and s2i strategies result in runnable images, but the custom build strategy can be used to create any resulting objects. These can be .jar files or Python packages, for example.
- A BuildConfig: some fields of the config is: output: which is about what the build will produce, Strategy: means which build strategy the build will use, Source: inputs to the build, Triggers: events that can cause a build to run.
- Build triggers: - webhook, -Image change, -configuration change,
- The output of a build will result an ImageStream, ImageStreams are a nifty way to represent images in OpenShift.
- An ImageStream is an abstraction for referencing images within OpenShift.
- Operators: are a powerful pattern used within Kubernetes to automate many tasks within a cluster, and Red Hat OpenShift provides a great way to easily install and use them.
- In addition to deployments and pods there is other resources, called custom resource definitions (CRDs), a custom resource is simply a new endpoint in the Kubernetes API that stores a collection of API objects.
- On their own, custom resources aren't overly useful—they let you store and retrieve data in the Kubernetes API, but they don't change the actual state of the cluster. To change the state, you need custom controllers.

- Custom controllers interpret the custom resource data stored in the API as a desired state, and as with all controllers, work to maintain that state.
- Combining custom resources and custom controllers gives a true declarative API like Pods possess. The combination of these two concepts has come to be known as the "Operator pattern."
- An operator is a way to package, deploy, and manage a Kubernetes native application, which is an application that is deployed on and managed by Kubernetes.
- If you want to deploy a whole application, you could first create a custom resource for that app. You would also need to deploy a controller for that CRD. The core of the process is the operator logic, which needs to determine how to reconcile the actual and desired states. So, if an instance of the CRD is declared, which Kubernetes objects (whether native objects or other CRDs) need to be created?
- Istio is a commonly used service mesh. A service mesh is a dedicated layer for making service-to-service communication secure and reliable.
- Istio provides connection, security, control and observability